

A QUALITATIVE STUDY ON POST-NATAL PANDEMIC EFFECT – WITH REFERENCE TO INDIAN IT EMPLOYEES

Jenesiszodykha V¹

Dr. R. V. Suganya²

Abstract:

The COVID-19 epidemic has produced an unparalleled transformation in the entire globe and the greatest disruption to all aspects of human history. This article uses qualitative analysis to evaluate how COVID-19 has affected workers in the IT (Information Technology) industry and its connected services. Due to the profound changes the epidemic has wrought in their cultural, occupational, and private lives, these individuals have experienced mental, physical, and social effects. Twenty-five persons were personally interviewed for the suggested qualitative study, and in-depth penetrating questions were used to better comprehend the emotional dynamics that eventually affected the way they live and who they are as individuals. The analysis's goal is to investigate and comprehend how the epidemic has affected the IT industry's organizational and management system, as well as the workers' work-life balance and social trends. I have frequently conducted the COVID-19 behavioral pattern identification about effects on social, organizational, and workplace culture aspects. The study also emphasizes how humans behave in reaction to difficulties and painful occurrences brought on by this outbreak. This study tries to comprehend the actualities of how businesses interact with their staff and alter their capital and policy practices to promote stable growth. It has been predicted and examined how the COVID-19 pandemic will affect the IT industry, both positively and negatively, as well as the post-COVID-19 environment.

Keywords: COVID-19, Information Technology, work-life balance.

Introduction:

Wuhan City, Hubei Province, China, is where the current coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) epidemic began in December 2019. The COVID-19 pandemic outbreak has primarily affected people's life and has been implicated as a major factor in an increase in death cases around the world. In addition to affecting general human problems, the epidemic has brought about terrible political and financial crises in the afflicted countries. In addition to posing a threat to the world, COVID-19 has also been identified as a significant contributor to social inequality and an insufficient rate of social advancement (Hung C, Wang, et.al., 2020).

¹ Research Scholar, Department of Commerce, Vels University, Chennai – 600117. Mailid: jenesis.zodykha@gmail.com

² Assistant Professor, Department of Commerce, Vels University, Chennai – 600117. Mailid: suganya.sms@velsuniv.ac.in sugan9979@gmail.com

In relation to this plague, isolation, social seclusion, lockdowns, and releases have all become trendy terms. Containment has, however, previously been thought to be a successful method of containing pandemics. Its name derives from the Italian phrase "quaranta giorni," which was used to describe the quarantine of ships for forty days during the bubonic plague pandemic in the fourteenth century (Waxman, 2020). Nevertheless, the necessity of quarantine has brought to a virtual physical and commercial freeze. Individuals' current leisure routines have been disturbed because of being compelled to remain indoors. Governments have enacted the freedom constraints in the pretext of a safety issue. It has turned out to be among the worst setbacks for the global IT/ITeS industry ever since 2009 economic meltdown. It has turned out to be among the worst setbacks for the global IT/ITeS industry ever since 2009 economic meltdown. Beginning in March 2020, all areas proclaimed national shutdowns, which cleared the ground for huge changes in the IT industries. Throughout the epidemic, the ITeS industry has been comparatively stable. It was significantly less affected than other industries, and because technology was adopted more quickly and there was still a need among their wide range of clients, it recovered far more quickly within a matter of quarters. Therefore, amid this setback, quarter of Indian enterprises affirmed that overall goals to increase company activities during the following season were still on schedule. (Unidas, 2021). In this essay, I'll try to examine and evaluate the COVID-19 pandemic's consequences and the corresponding prevention measures, such as isolating, and shutdowns succeeded by releases. The ensuing periodic and sector-specific halting of industrial and business activity is having a knock-on effect on the information technology industry and its linked industries, which have become omnipresent in these trying circumstances.

Research Methodology:

This study tries to comprehend how IT workers are feeling and the broad repercussions they are experiencing in these eras of uncertainty, confusion, and dramatic changes. To collect the necessary qualitative data, I conducted telephone individual interviews while retaining my social distance and isolate. 25 people over the age of 21 who live in different cities across India make up the research population. These people work in numerous industries and organizations and hold a variety of titles and positions. I conducted targeted, semi-structured interviews. Work-life balance, shifts in company culture, and group relations, particularly those involving coworkers, neighbors, and relatives, were the topics of the questions. They can speak themselves freely because the questions were open-ended. I was able to gain deeper information as a result. I tried to examine the information gathered from the conversations using the unique inputs noted in each message and came to both general and specific conclusions. This has made it easier to conduct a proper method for impact evaluation. In the paper's final section, I present my results.

Findings:

The finding has given below on four bases. They are organization, business environment, Socializing and private life.

a. *Organization:*

The full significance of job digitization is starting to take shape. Particularly in nations such as India, in which individuals initially hesitant to manage businesses and activities online prior to COVID 19 but have since mastered the technique, it is beginning to make a great deal of reason. The handling of personal information has improved across the online digital work system. Numerous businesses with plenty of cash are attempting to update their services and equipment to give all users improved amenities as well as safety and protection. Facilities businesses, which are common in growing sectors, are hiring new workers, but a lot of them are losing money and are being forced to dismiss their staff members, reduce salaries, or even give up their infrastructure. The organizations' budgeting practices have undergone substantial adjustments. To demonstrate their capacity to carry out advanced technological initiatives, most enterprises will need to invest in the latest age technology, if they haven't done so previously. The biggest firms can buy smaller organizations thanks to the depreciation. Fewer smaller groups are gaining out of these changes, yet many are forced to close their businesses because of a lack of funding. It has been advised that staff members of numerous firms shift their technology from SEZs and desktops to their distant venues. Due to the pandemic's severe effects on the entire globe, even customers outside of India are asking for delayed rent and payment obligations.

Additions and upgrades are being made to many platforms, along with the strengthening of security fixes. Regular work administration monitors are used by businesses like Tech Mahindra to keep track of staffing levels. Companies in machine learning, deep learning, and cryptocurrency are becoming more and more popular among companies such as Infosys, Wipro, TCS, and Tech Mahindra. Other businesses have been leveraging their in-house portals to inform their staff regarding the most recent technological advancements and technological trends. Yorbit, an eLearning portal offered by Mindtree, enables its staff members to upgrade their skills. With the use of its Artificial learning system, Next, Capgemini pushes organized learning to its staff members, assisting them with their tasks.

b. *Business Environment:*

The administrators of call centers as well as other rear services for overseas firms are facing significant technical challenges as a result of constraints on everyday activities. Projects that manage confidential material, like monetary operations for international bank clients, are particularly challenging in this regard. To boost total efficiency, there is a greater emphasis on administration and governance teaching methods, such as online teamwork and fiscal learning for non-administrative positions. Nevertheless, workers in India generally experience delay due to the absence of effective computer, connection, and web access, specifically those who live in rural areas. However, meetings may help avoid misunderstandings when they are conducted effectively, particularly now that everyone must have paperwork. For the majority of workers, the performance level has altered.

Certain types of women, living with disabilities people, and various other groups of

individuals who are unable to adhere to traditional workplace hours have been given new chances by this epidemic. Additionally, it is currently possible to hire the most qualified applicants regardless of where they are situated. Operating for different customers currently gives numerous workers, particularly freelancers, a greater sensation of financial stability. Nonetheless, in this economy, it is difficult for horizontal workers to acquire new jobs. The common consensus is that retraining or upskilling freshmen is more economical than lateral hires. Some individuals have been compelled to take positions with lesser categories or just with less favorable compensation. Cognizant has been obliged to halt most of the progressive recruitment all across India's positions and levels because of the weak demand climate and interruption of numerous economic operations, with a handful of outliers in tech positions (Pokhrel, S., & Chhetri, R. 2021).

The bright side of these circumstances is how highly valued commitment and loyalty are by many businesses. They go above and above to support their staff in every way they can. Amartya Sen is true when he says that acknowledging variety across many civilizations is crucial today.

c. *Socializing:*

Impacts on Individual lives individuals are trying to quickly acclimate to the VUCA workplace. Workers are developing unique and original answers to both their private and professional concerns. Home-based work has compelled them to adopt an approach of autonomous working, become more focused, dedicated, plus cope all their issues at their different stages especially when they are collaborating with one another. The elimination of commuting, that saves a significant amount of time, has resulted in the staff being timelier and fully organized for their appointments and talks.

There are various types of people that use their leisure time to unwind, heal, and pick up new activities (Vajpai, 2021). Many categories of individuals are trying tirelessly than they did previously for a range of reasons, including a heavier workload, more talent initiatives, and a renewed desire to perform tasks from the convenience of their own homes. Additionally, they are developing better time management skills in an effort to support work-life balance. Many individuals are thankful for the safer world and are experiencing spectacular natural wonders for the first time.

It is evident that the ages that were born first before twenties are increasingly accustomed to living in a digital world. For those who resisted using advanced technology before the epidemic, this is a whole unique adventure. In addition to these, the research showed that global injustices like racism still exist. It confirmed what Lemert Mishrif, A. (2021) had stated, "Colonialism is now abolished, but discrimination endures in the frequently secret relationship whites engage Blacks." Additionally, some workers are under stress because they or their loved ones are being quarantined. Most staff have seen significant changes in team relationships. Despite physical separation, group members' knowledge and collaboration have generally improved. People care for their neighborhoods as well as one other, as I was able to observe with my first respondent. Despite a couple of outliers, the amount of support and love

they receive from one another has multiplied greatly, keeping them upbeat and joyous. But because of the shortage of facial expression human contact, anyone enjoys getting out with their relatives and friends, and incidences of sadness, stress, anxiety disorder, sleep difficulties, and other mental diseases are on the rise.

Discussions:

A new method of living will emerge after COVID-19. Along with changing personal and social relationships, it will also offer work company's culture style new definition. Businesses will need to develop more cooperative management strategies. To engage workers at all levels, main decision must be more flattened or decorticated. Microsoft and others have indeed explicitly announced that their staff members will remain able to work from home over the coming few seasons. The need for AI, ML, information science, cloud computing, PAAS, and technological applications will keep rising. But the rising usage of AI and the "onshoring" of employment will have a significant influence on nations. The back-office activities of transnational companies have long benefited several businesses, particularly in emerging nations like India (Mishra, 2020). The use of Cloud technology will be the main source of the upcoming ideas. In the case of corporations with lots of cash, several purchases and mergers can be anticipated. Enterprise resource management software will be used more effectively going forward, especially since most firms will be functioning primarily digitally. It would undoubtedly be a new planet to live in, that much is certain. Everyone has been forced by the current epidemic to immediately deploy resources to the distant work atmosphere. Most Indian enterprises have rapidly adopted the Work-From-Home or Take a job model, despite major infrastructure-related issues in certain regions of India. One amongst India's key industries for promotes healthy during the Pandemic's initial stages is the IT industry, which paved the way in implementing work methods throughout COVID-19. The study looks at the overall effects of the work practices used by leading Indian IT organizations. The two major mixed work methods utilized by the significant IT organizations selected for this research are Work-From-Home and Collaborate.

Conclusion:

The investigation demonstrates the broad variations in attitudes toward the epidemic and responses to its impacts on the information technology industry.

The planet is now completely networked civilization instead of the old civilization with actual human contact because of the present era. Individuals who live solitary, particularly individuals who prefer not to communicate their concerns and anxiety with anyone else their members of the family to put in extra effort to deal with stressful circumstances. Information asymmetry can be worsened by total social isolation, including family (Kolluru et al., 2021). People today recognize the value of social connection. On a personal basis, I felt that people in nuclear families are better able to complete their task than people in mixed families. While working from home is largely beneficial for assisting and comprehending members of the family, it can

occasionally cause overburdened employees to feel neglected by their loved ones. People are very frustrated when they can't help their aging parents, small kids, or other individuals who might need them. Improved handling of these problems is necessary to prevent the spread of gossip, confusion, and fear of losing out. Paradoxically, individuals who ask for flexible work schedules and methods have trouble adjusting to this degree of adaptability.

References:

Huang, C., Wang, Y., Li, X., Ren, L., Zhao, J., Hu, Y., ... & Cao, B. (2020). Clinical features of patients infected with 2019 novel coronavirus in Wuhan, China. *The lancet*, 395(10223), 497-506.

Kolluru, M., Krishnan, K., & Kolluru, S. K. (2021, December 1). Post COVID-19 Work Strategies and Implications: Insight on Indian IT Sector. *ECONOMICS*, 9(2), 49–72. <https://doi.org/10.2478/eoik-2021-0014>

Mishra, N. P., Das, S. S., Yadav, S., Khan, W., Afzal, M., Alarifi, A., Kenawy, E. R., Ansari, M. T., Hasnain, M. S., & Nayak, A. K. (2020). Global impacts of pre- and post-COVID-19 pandemic: Focus on socio-economic consequences. *Sensors International*, 1(July). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sintl.2020.100042>

Mishrif, A. (2021). *Technology Adaption As Survival Strategy For Small And Medium Enterprises During COVID-19*. 1–17.

Pokhrel, S., & Chhetri, R. (2021). A Literature Review on Impact of COVID-19 Pandemic on Teaching and Learning. *Higher Education for the Future*, 8(1), 133–141. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2347631120983481>

Unidas, N., Nations, U., & on Indian Industry, C. (2021). *IT enabled services in the post-pandemic economy: new opportunities for relations between India and Latin America*.

Vajpai, I. (2021). Qualitative Assessment of the Impact of Post-COVID-19 on Indian IT Sector Employees. *Researchgate.Net*, February. https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Ishani-Vajpai/publication/349376144_Qualitative_Assessment_of_the_Impact_of_Post_COVID-19_on_Indian_IT_Sector_Employees/links/602d2719a6fdcc37a831bf15/Qualitative-Assessment-of-the-Impact-of-Post-COVID-19-on-Indian-IT

Waxman, O. B. (2020, March 9). The Grand Princess Has Docked in California. Here's What to Know About the History of Quarantine on Ships. *Time*. Retrieved October 15, 2022, from <https://time.com/5799525/coronavirus-covid19-quarantine-ships-history/>